

AI-READI Steering Committee Charter

Version History

Version / Date	Description of changes
All versions	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7641684 This DOI represents all versions, and will always resolve to the latest one.
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Charge:

The Steering Committee is responsible for strategic leadership and general oversight of the Bridge2AI OT2 Data Generation Project known as AI Ready and Equitable Atlas for Diabetes Insights (AI-READI).

Responsibilities of the Steering Committee:

- Lead and oversee the AI-READI project including strategic project-wide decisions.

- Review, provide feedback, and approve any scientific manuscripts or work products released in relation to the AI-READI project.

Composition and Membership:

The Steering Committee is chaired by the lead PI of the project.

- The voting members of the steering committee are:
 - Chair
 - 1 representative (Co-I or MPI) from each of the following modules: Teaming, ETAI, Standards, Tools, Skills and Workforce
 - 1 representative from each of the clinical sites, representing the Data module together: UAB, UCSD, and UW
- One additional member per module and clinical site (non-voting members; can represent their module as *voting* members if the designated voting member cannot attend the meeting)
- Program staff from the NIH, such as Program Leader, Program Coordinators, Program Officers, and Project Scientists may serve as non-voting members
- External Program Consultants (ex officio, non-voting)
- Project managers from across AI-READI may join as non-voting members.

The members of the Steering Committee may be removed for cause by the NIH or upon vote of 7/9 (~70%) of the voting members of the Steering Committee. Possible causes shall include – but are not limited to – failure to attend three consecutive meetings, unless the absence is justified for personal reasons, emergencies or failure to meet the expectations outlined below for three consecutive meetings. Justifiable excuses will be discussed and accepted/denied at the discretion of the Chair.

Meetings:

The Steering Committee (SC) will hold monthly meetings at the outset of the program. The SC meetings are to be attended by invitation only and are only open to its members. To be a validly constituted meeting, at least 6 of the 9 voting members of the Steering Committee must be present. If less than 6 members are present then the meeting may still be held but no votes will be cast. Voting members of the Steering Committee may designate non-voting members to execute their vote in their absence. The Chair must be notified at least 24 hours in advance along with the name of the designated replacement. If both of the regular members of a module or clinical site plan to be absent during the meeting, with advanced approval, a designee from their team may attend the meeting and may also serve as the voting member for the occasion if authorized by the substituted regular voting member. Additional attendees may be invited to the SC meetings as needed upon suggestion by the SC members.

Expectations of the Steering Committee members:

- Read meeting materials in advance and come prepared to contribute substantively to the work of the Committee
- Present 1-2 slides of highlighted accomplishments and set-backs for the module

- Update the project-wide Gantt chart prior to the meeting
- Actively engage in discussions and contribute expertise to decision-making processes
- Provide timely review and feedback on documents when solicited
- Participate in surveys and information gathering as appropriate

Agenda items:

There will be a standing call for agenda items up to one week prior to each Steering Committee meeting; any AI-READI project team member can suggest an agenda item.

Voting and Decision Making:

The Steering Committee will use a collaborative, majority-based decision-making process that requires the approval of at least 6 out of 9 (~66%) of the voting members of the Steering Committee for any Steering Committee decision. If a voting member must abstain from voting due to a conflict of interest related to the matter at hand, the voting member should designate another non-voting member as the voter in their stead. If there are issues that the Steering Committee cannot reach a consensus on, the Steering Committee will provide NIH with a summary of the areas of disagreement, and NIH will work with the Steering Committee to attempt to resolve such disagreements. If such disagreements cannot be resolved, the chair with discussions with the NIH will determine the appropriate course of action.

Amendments:

Amendments to this charter will require the approval of NIH and the Steering Committee.

Reporting:

The Steering Committee will keep regular minutes of its meetings and provide a record of these to the SC prior to each upcoming meeting.